

THE PROBLEM OF CONCEPTUAL METAPHOR

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7294302>

ABSTRACT:

The article deals the metaphors are considered to be one such type of linguistic deviation that leads to foregrounding and defamiliarization. However, the assumption that these violations are deliberately used for the sake of drawing attention to their status as being violations becomes problematic when considered in light of the findings of Conceptual Metaphor Theory.

Keywords: metaphor, conceptual, concept, structure, phenomenon, linguistic expressions.

INTRODUCTION

According to Lakoff and Johnson [4, 44] metaphor exists at the level of culture, social relations, and individual here-and-now experience. For Lakoff, the locus of metaphor is not in language at all but in the way we conceptualise one mental domain in terms of another. The view that metaphor plays a fundamental structural role in organizing our conceptual systems, rather than serving a deviant rhetorical effect, is now generally accepted. Nonetheless, the traditional assumptions of metaphor would deserve to recall briefly as follows:

- All everyday language is literal, and none is metaphorical.
- All concepts entailing full comprehending can be realised literally, without metaphor.
- Only literal language can be true.

The reason for the distinction of significance between this traditional view and contemporary tenet is based on the discovery of the phenomenon conceptual metaphor. It is the very system of metaphor that our conceptual system employed so in an intensive way in daily life, mostly for the abstract concepts. In any languages there are numerous instances that are necessarily and spontaneously used in everyday life but not for rhetorical purposes.

The past many years have seen a radical reappraisal of the role of metaphor in both language, and general cognitive processing. Once viewed as a peripheral and somewhat aberrant or deviant phenomenon, metaphor is now recognized to play a central role in the organization and acquisition of conceptual structure. From this perspective, language is viewed as

fundamentally metaphorical in nature and metaphor is given a central role in the development of conceptual structure. The idea that the conceptual metaphors systematically structure the way that many domains are understood has subsequently been used to help explain, among other things, the nature of emotion concepts [3, 77] and the meaning of idioms [2, 137-138]. A conceptual metaphor is a generalization that can be inferred from diverse surface forms of language to inferred system of thoughts [1, 107].

Conceptual metaphors typically employ a more abstract concept as target and a more concrete or physical concept as their source. For instance, metaphors such as 'the days – the more abstract or target concept- ahead' or 'giving my time' rely on more concrete concepts, thus expressing time as a -more concrete- path into physical space or as a substance -that can be handled and offered as a gift. Different conceptual metaphors tend to be invoked when the speaker is trying to make a case for a certain point of view or course of action. For instance, we associate 'the days ahead' more with leadership, and 'giving my time' more with bargaining – if time is a substance, clearly, it should be treated for things of substance, and this metaphor makes that more obvious than the path metaphor. Selection of such metaphors tends to be directed by a subconscious or implicit purpose, in the mind of him or her who chooses them.

A conceptual domain is any coherent organization of experience. To see these target domains by making use of such source domains as war, journey, food, it is worth considering some classic examples of each from Lakoff and Johnson. The small capitals for the statement of conceptual metaphors and italics for metaphorical linguistic expressions [4, 102-103]:

AN ARGUMENT IS WAR.

Your claims are indefensible.

He a/lacked every weak point in my argument.

His criticisms were right on lodge.

I demolished his argument.

If you use that strategy, he'll wipe you out.

He shot down all of my arguments.

LOVE IS A JOURNEY.

Look how far we've come.

We're at a crossroads.

We'll just have to go our separate ways.

We can't turn back now.

I don't think this relationship is going anywhere.

Where we are?

This relationship is a dead – end street.

We're just spinning our wheels.

Our marriage is on the rocks.

We've gotten off the track.

THEORIES ARE BUILDINGS.

Is that the foundation for your theory?

The theory needs more support.

We need to construct a strong argument for that.

We need to buttress the theory with solid arguments.

So far we have put together only the framework of the theory.

IDEAS ARE FOOD.

All this paper has in it are raw facts, half-baked ideas, and warmed-over theories.

There are too many facts here for me to digest them all.

I just can't swallow that claim.

That's food for thought.

She devoured the book.

Let's let that idea simmer on the back burner for a while.

Let me stew over that for a while.

CONCLUSIONS

Summing up of all what has just been said we can conclude that conceptual structure is not merely a matter of the intellect - it involves all the natural dimensions of our experience, including aspects of our sense experiences: colour, shape, texture, sound, etc.

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